

TRAITS OF AN EFFECTIVE KOREAN LANGUAGE TEACHER

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The issue of the ideal teacher is an ongoing topic. It has been addressed and talked about in the teaching and learning field for long. The teacher is one of the main factors that has a lot of influence on students' achievement, performance and their success (Zainab Al Balushy, 2011 cited in Melek Koc, 2012). In addition to the teacher's knowledge about the subject matters, other characteristics of the teacher such as teaching skills, teaching styles and personal traits such as broad knowledge about Korea will also impact the students' learning attitudes, motivation and the learning outcomes to some extent. According to Adams and Pierce (1999) having many years of experience doesn't guarantee expert teaching; experience is useful only when the teacher continually engages in self-reflection and modifies classroom techniques to better serve the needs of students. Apart from good teaching skills that teachers need to have, personal traits are also equally important because they also play a vital role in the success of learning. It is important to study the perceptions of Korean learners about learning and teaching. The question of what makes a good teacher is hardly a new subject. A quick glance at the literature reveals that the result of almost any study has been a list of characteristics which should be possessed by teachers in order to be called "effective". For example, Raymont and Welton (cited in Campbell, Kyriakides, Muijs, & Robinson, 2004), were probably the first who tried to develop propositions regarding effective teaching. *They introduced five propositions: planning, teacher-pupil interaction, lesson structure, core teaching skills, and the power of the individual teacher to teach.* These five propositions are interdependent and really make sense when only considered as a unit. Also, Thompson and Greer (2004) explored the reflections of university students regarding the characteristics of their favorite teachers from whom they were able to learn. Data collected from the students indicated that there are twelve common characteristics that emerged as central to what students conceptualize as good teaching. *Those twelve characteristics were displaying fairness, having a positive outlook, being prepared, using a personal touch, possessing a sense of humor, possessing creativity, admitting mistakes, being forgiving, respecting students, maintaining high expectations, showing compassion, and developing a sense of belonging for students.* They suggested that all those characteristics center on the theme of caring. If lecturers are to be responsive to student needs and improve the effectiveness of student outcomes, they must first understand what students define as effective lecturing.

Besides, effective teachers have been described as 'active' teachers who make maximum use of *instruction time, present material in ways to meet student needs, monitor programs and progress and plan opportunities for students to apply newly acquired concepts and skills* (Brophy & Good, 1986; Witcher, Onwuegbuzie, & Minor, 2001). Diamond defined an effective teacher as "the one who conducts effective teaching which produces beneficial and purposeful student learning through the use of appropriate procedures." (Diamond; 1998, cited in Strickland, 1998, p.83).

So, different views of language teaching lead to different views as to what the essential skills of teaching are, and to different approaches to the preparation of teachers. Students do know how teachers feel about them. If they think you don't care for them, you have already lost

them. “The aim of teaching is simple: it is to make students’ learning possible...To teach is to make an assumption about what and how the student learns; therefore, to teach well implies learning about students’ learning” (Ramsden, 1992, p. 124). Although the content in Korean language teaching is more varied and scattered, the teaching model is more fixed, as opposed to other language teaching, Korean teaching pays more attention to the connection between vocabulary and grammar. Therefore, the teacher needs to emphasize the learning of key and difficult points in the development of teaching activities, and strengthen the guidance to students, taking into account the requirements of the syllabus and interpretations of Korean content. So students need to reinforce their learning and understanding of grammatical constructs and teacher-guided learning of the Skills are acquired and learned to enhance the value of teaching Korean language courses (Tingting Shi, 2020, p.39). Good teachers know that by listening to and working with colleagues, parents, other professionals and community members, they can inspire students and improve their learning. Everybody wants to have an ideal teacher while studying somewhere. However, when it comes to a definition of a perfect teacher it appears to be not so easy to give it, because different teachers are successful in different ways. For example, some are easy-going and charismatic, while others are quiet and not very sociable but in spite of the difference in personalities, all good teachers have some common qualities that help them to become the best ones (Radmacher & Martin, 2001). Combining above mentioned features there can be given some conceptualized findings which define teacher’s competence. They are as follows:

- *Content knowledge about Korean and Korea*
- *Pedagogic content knowledge (the ability to contextualize, situate, and personalize the content for the learners)*
- *General pedagogic knowledge (principles and strategies of classroom management and organization regardless of content matter)*
- *Curriculum knowledge (materials and programs that are the ‘tools of trade’ for teachers) which are actual present time*
- *Knowledge of learners and their characteristics*
- *Knowledge of educational contexts, and contexts (the group, the classroom, the district, the community)*
- *Knowledge of educational ends, purposes and values*

Then, good teachers should be motivating. Good teachers always succeed in inspiring their students both in class and out of class. Teachers have the power to inspire, through their attitudes, actions, and even through the lessons.

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